

Section 4: Climatic Resilience Initiative for Pavement Infrastructure

COST ACTION 24141 CRIPI

Seyed Reza Omranian

Soha Ahmadi

15/01/2026

Section 4: CRIPI

Session 4

CRIPI

Prof Wim Van den bergh, *University of Antwerp, CRIPI Chair*

Prof Aikaterina Varveri, *TU Delft, Leader of WG 3*

Prof Joao Santos, *University of Twente, Leader of RPA*

15/01/2026

Climatic Resilience Initiative for Pavement Infrastructure

Wim Van den bergh, Chair
Ana Jiménez del Barco Carrión, Vice-chair

CRIFI - European Network

- More than 140 partners and 27 countries (2025-2029)
- Establishing a **multidisciplinary framework** that enhances **pavement resilience to climate change** through scientific innovation, advanced monitoring, and improved sustainability assessment,
- Supporting stakeholders with tools and strategies for **building and maintaining durable, adaptive, and sustainable road infrastructure across Europe.**
- Capacity Building and Research Coordination
 - Funding for meetings, events, scientific missions
 - Supporting young researchers and innovator
 - Application is always open to join

15/01/2026

CA - How does it work?

CA - Instruments

- COST Principles: Capacity Building, Gender and ITC balance, networking, supporting Young researchers and innovators
- Budget: +130k/yr
 - Networking Activities Events
 - Meetings: Workgroup, Core Group and Management Committees
 - Training Schools
 - Activities Grant Awarding Process
 - Mobility of researchers and innovators
 - Presentations at conferences
 - Dissemination: social media, ...

CA - Working Groups

- **WG1. Climate factors, pavement resilience, and risk assessment** (Gordon Airey; Jo Sias)
 - Climate factors, Pavement resilience, Risk assessment
- **WG2. Materials** (Miomir Miljkovic; Bernhard Hofko)
 - Advanced concepts of materials, Critical aspects of the materials' resilience, Characterization of the material's response under climatic impacts
- **WG3. Pavement** (Evangelos Manthos; Aikaterina Varveri)
 - Climate change impact on pavements, implemented pavement technologies to address climate change mitigation
 - Suitability assessment of implemented pavement technologies, Ongoing research on pavements to address climate change
 - Pavement system guidelines for addressing climate change
- **WG4. Pavement health monitoring and resilient index** (Pierre Hornyh; Nizar Lajnef)
 - Information technology (IT), Sensors, Road Inspection
- **WG5. Sustainability Assessment** (Davide Lo Presti;
 - Methodology to develop consequential LCA for pavement, Sustainability Assessment of climate-resilient paving materials and activities
 - Principles of climate-resilient pavement
- **WG6. Coordination and Communication** (Seyed Reza Omranian; Konieczna Katarzyna)

Asphalt Innovation Symposium 2025

December 11
Antwerp

University of Antwerp
| SuPAR | Sustainable Pavements
and Asphalt Research

University
of Antwerp

Sessie 4

Sharing visions and plans on WG3 of CRIP
COST Action on pavement resilience

Katerina Varveri

TU Delft

CRIP

Presentation slides: Assoc. Prof. Manthos | Assoc. Prof. Varveri | Prof. Erkens

CRIFI WORK GROUPS

WG1. Climate factors, pavement resilience, and risk assessment

WG2. Materials

WG3. Pavement Leader: AUTH, Co-Leader: TU Delft

WG4. Pavement health monitoring and resilient index

WG5. Sustainability Assessment

WG6. Communication and dissemination

WG3 within the CRIPI work programme

Why CRIPI-WG3 on pavements is important?

Climate change

- Climate change more and more part of our lives
 - increase in worldwide average temperature
 - gradual changes in average weather patterns
 - more frequent extreme weather conditions
- The extreme conditions get the most attention
 - Disruptive
 - Impressive footage

Global News

'Rotten rock': Climate change altering the face of Canadian mountaineering
19 hours ago

CBS News

Climate change could be impacting emergence of cicadas
59 minutes ago

Yahoo

Cicadas are back, but climate change is messing with them
3 hours ago

The Weather Network

Rising seas force Panama Indigenous families to leave island homes
1 day ago

More news →

Perspectives :

Michael R. Bloom...
Bloomberg

Michael Bloomberg:
Climate Change Needs to
Harness Power of
Markets

The problem of climate

Juliet Kinsman
Yahoo News Singap...

OPINION - Earth Day
2024: As the climate
descends into chaos, we
need to be mindful of...

Today is Earth Day. Mean

Quesnel Cariboo ...

FOREST INK: Climate
change could be
mitigated by Peatland
forest mosaics

Peatland forest mosaics are

Climate change

Surface temperature trends over the last 50 years

Human and Natural Influences on Global Temperature

Climate change and infrastructure

- As other systems, pavements are affected both by the gradual and extreme effects
- Both (repeated) extreme weather events and gradual climate change can result in
 - Decreased pavement performance
 - Reduced lifetimes
 - Increased maintenance needs and costs

Climate change and pavements

- Both extreme weather events and gradual climate changes can result in
 - operational disruptions
 - transportation infrastructure damage
 - changing requirements for infrastructure
- What does that mean for pavements?
 - designed and maintained based on historical local climate conditions → sensitive to climate change
 - monitoring, maintenance and reconstruction practices need to be assessed to design for future conditions

Climate change and pavements

Extreme rainfall

- **Immediate effects**

- Overloading drainage systems → flooding of roads, pavement saturation, weakening soft shoulder → traffic hindrance and safety (splash and spray, aqua planning)

- **Long(er) term effects**

- Increased soil moisture levels → risk of landslides, reduced structural integrity of roads & bridges
- Erosion of asphalt and soft shoulder, removing coverage leading to seepage and blocking of drains (fines)
- Accelerated deterioration of structural and/or material performance

Climate change and pavements

Higher temperatures / higher frequency of hot days, droughts

- **Immediate effects**

- wildfires → pavement damage, non-closing/opening bridges, buckling of rail, spalling of concrete
- Accumulation of material on road surface during dry spell → skidding during first rain

- **Long(er) term effects**

- reduced stiffness, less load carrying capacity,
- increased aging,

Hitteprotocol op de weg

Climate change and pavements

- **Soil shrinkage** due to drought → cracking
- Water in and/or on pavements leads to **erosion of bitumen**
- The **pavement structure** as a whole is affected due to **reduction of bearing capacity** of base & subgrade
- High temperatures can cause **permanent deformation, lower stiffness and bearing capacity, excessive ageing**
- **Moisture/water** in combination **with freezing or traffic loading** can lead to potholes & other damage in relatively young pavements.

WG3 Objectives

WG3.A. Climate change impact on pavements

WG3.B. Implemented pavement technologies to address climate change mitigation

WG3.C. Suitability assessment of implemented pavement technologies

WG3.D. Creation of a database of cutting-edge research conducted globally, focusing on solutions that have not yet been implemented.

WG3.E. Pavement system guidelines for addressing climate change

WG3 Tasks

T3.A.1. Geographical mapping of climate change parameter intensity

T3.A.2 Identification of the most influential environment stressors for pavements in the current and future climate conditions

T3.B.1 Description of the latest materials, design methods, structural pavement systems, and existing/developing technologies currently employed in pavement engineering to address the effects of climate change.

T3.C.1 Assessment of the adequacy of current methods for future implementation

T3.D.1 Identification of ongoing research activities

T3.E.1 Recommendations and guidelines for the design and construction of climate-resilient pavements

TASK 3.A.1

Geographical mapping of climate change parameter intensity

TASK 3.A.2

Identification of the most influential environmental stressors for pavements in the current and future climate conditions

TASK 3.B.1

Description of the latest materials, design methods, structural pavement systems, and existing/developing technologies currently employed in pavement engineering to address the effects of climate change.

TASK 3.C.1

Assessment of current methods for future implementation

FOCUS

Assess the vulnerability of climate mitigation technologies with respect to global prediction techniques for the progression of climate change.

INPUT

WG3.A (T3.C. 1), Questionnaires will be distributed to road agencies, authorities, and contractors to gather their opinions on the effectiveness of implemented technologies in addressing specific climate change challenges

OUTPUT

Survey findings and analysis on the effectiveness of implemented pavement technologies used for addressing climate change

TASK 3.D.1

Identification of ongoing research activities

TASK 3.E.1

Recommendations and guidelines for the design and construction of climate-resilient pavements

FOCUS

Formulating comprehensive guidelines for the design and construction of entire pavement systems in the context of climate change evolution.

INPUT

WG1, WG2, WG5, WG3A, WG3B, WG3C, WG3D

OUTPUT

Best practices manual for climate-resilient pavement construction.

Geographical distribution of WG3 participants

Total number of participants so far: **69**
Coming from **23** countries

Expertise of WG3 participants

WG3 Next steps

- The first online meeting of WG3 will be organized at the **end of January 2026**. Specific date will be announced.
- WG3 scientific missions: potential workshops physical meetings, and seminars will be decided in collaboration with the other WG leaders and announced in due time.

Would you like to join us?

Contact

Assoc. Prof. Evangelos Manthos, AUTH, Greece
emanthos@civil.auth.gr

Assoc. Prof. A. (Katerina) Varveri, TU Delft, The Netherlands
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Sessie 4

Resilience Pavement Association (RPA)

Mission, Vision and Activities

Joao Santos

University of Twente (NL)

Leadership

Leader: Joao Santos
j.m.oliveiradossantos@utwente.nl

Co-Leader: `Soha Ahmadi
Soha.Ahmadi@uantwerpen.be

Mission

Pavement Resilience

Photo Credits:Tinnakorn Jorruang

Mission

“To advance the **science, practice, and policy** of **pavement resilience** by connecting researchers, industry, road authorities and policy makers to create **climate-proof, resource-efficient, and digitally enabled** road infrastructure.”

Pavement Resilience

Vision

"A European road network that is **climate- and cyber-resilient, low-carbon**, and **designed to withstand the future of mobility**, including electrification, automation, extreme weather, cyberattacks and materials scarcity."

Value Proposition

The RPA provides:

- **A scientific home** for researchers working on climate adaptation, resilience, sustainability and circularity.
- **A trusted interface** between academia, industry, policy makers and road authorities.
- **Shared knowledge and tools** that help Europe design pavements that last longer, perform better, and contribute to climate goals.
- **A coordinated voice** to influence European policy, standards, and funding priorities.

Activities

Meetings

- Presential (with hybrid option)
- Online

Pavement Resilience Knowledge Hub

- Papers
- Tools
- Datasets
- Tutorials
- Projects map

Activities

Living Pavement Resilience Handbook

Quarterly "Pavement Resilience Scientific Highlights Digest" Newsletter

"Challenges Briefs"

Quarterly Online Seminar Series on Pavement Resilience

Activities

Bi-annual short-term mobility Calls for Young Researchers

Training activities for Young Researchers

Roundtable Dialogues

Pavement Resilience Workshop

2026 Planning

2027 Planning

Join Us!

Fill in the (short) questionnaire

Questions and Suggestions

Leader: Joao Santos
j.m.oliveiradossantos@utwente.nl

Co-Leader: Soha Ahmadi
Soha.Ahmadi@uantwerpen.be

WG 6: Communication and dissemination

COST ACTION 24141 CRIPI

Seyed Reza Omranian
Katarzyna Konieczna

How to join CRIPI

Create e-COST account

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar displaying 'e-services.cost.eu/user/login'. The browser's tab bar shows several open tabs, including 'Spam (2)', '5.3 HMA Mix Desig...', 'World Academy of...', 'HORIZON-CLS-202...', 'Scientific Conferenc...', 'Watch Movies and T...', 'Chapter 2 FATIGUE...', and 'Describing graphs'. The main content area displays the e-COST login interface. At the top left is the 'cost' logo with the tagline 'EUROPEAN COOPERATION IN SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY' and a purple 'e-COST' banner. The main heading is 'e-COST The online platform of COST Association'. Below this are two input fields: 'Email *' and 'Password *'. A 'Remember me' checkbox is present below the password field. There are two links: 'Forgot password?' and 'New to e-COST? Create an account.'. A blue 'Login' button is located at the bottom right of the form. At the bottom of the page, there is a copyright notice: 'Copyright © 2008 - 2025 COST, All rights reserved. Disclaimer - Cookie Policy - Privacy Notice' and a version string: 'page displayed on: 10/12/2025 at 17:57 - version: 2025.13.4'.

15/01/2026

How to join CRIPI

Go to CRIPI COST Action

A screenshot of a web browser showing the CRIPI COST Action page. The browser's address bar displays 'cost.eu/actions/CA24141/'. The page header includes the COST logo (European Cooperation in Science & Technology) and navigation menus for 'COST Actions', 'Funding', and 'About'. A prominent green button says 'Open call Fund your network'. The main heading is 'CA24141 - Climatic Resilience Initiative for Pavement Infrastructure (CRIPI)'. Below this, there are tabs for 'Description', 'Management Committee', 'Main Contacts and Leadership', and 'Working Groups and Membership'. The 'Description' tab is active, showing a paragraph about climate change impacts on pavements. To the right, an 'Action Details' box lists 'MoU - 05/25', 'CSO Approval date - 19/05/2025', and 'Start date - 23/10/2025'.

15/01/2026

How to join CRIPI

- Description
- Management Committee
- Main Contacts and Leadership
- Working Groups and Membership**

Working Groups

Number	Title	Leader
1	Climate factors, pavement resilience, and risk assessment	Prof Gordon AIREY
2	Materials	Prof Miomir MILJKOVIĆ
3	Pavement	Dr Evangelos MANTHOS
	Pavement health monitoring and resilient index	Dr Pierre HORNYCH
	Sustainability Assessment	Dr Davide LO PRESTI
6	Communication and dissemination	Dr Seyed Reza OMRANIAN

Express your interest to join any of the working groups by applying below.

It is required to have an e-COST profile to submit your application. If needed, [create it first](#) and then click 'Apply'.

Apply

15/01/2026

Upcoming Events in 2026

MC yearly meeting
Granada (Hybrid)

CG quarterly meeting
Nantes (Hybrid)

Seminar/workshop
Nottingham (Hybrid)

RPA, YRI, Seminar, WG
Palermo (Hybrid)

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